

VARIOUS FORMS OF POWER TRANSITIONS IN COUNTRIES AND POTENTIAL CRISIS SITUATIONS

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Abstract: We evaluate the political processes occurring in the world using the example of developmental stages of countries with the same status and different systems. The impact of government changes and various forms of governance in these countries on society's life. Results of measures taken by their leaders during crisis periods.

Keywords: Republic, President, Monarchy, Parliament, Dictatorship, Society, Change of Government, Election, Revolution, Development, Crisis, Reform.

Over the past century, the current political map of the world has been shaped under the influence of various historical processes, with the emergence of countries specializing in large and small industries or agriculture. The gradual dismantling of colonial policies. In this context, the claims of powerful countries to territories, the First and Second World Wars, and the prospects and collapse of the socialist system deserve special attention. Under the influence of these historical events, the number of independent states in the world has steadily increased throughout the 20th and 21st centuries. Today, the world's political map includes 205 independent states (7 partially recognized, 194 fully recognized, and 4 unrecognized), as well as 28 autonomous states[1]. Of these countries, 149 are officially Republics and 45 are Monarchies, each with its own unique path of development.

When discussing the most developed and underdeveloped countries in the world and studying their differences, we observe that the main focus is on what groups or leaders have governed them, as well as the ethnic composition and historical origins of the population of that country. As an example, in 1945, after Japan's defeat in World War II, the Kuomintang came to power in China, followed by the Socialists. The last Emperor Pu Yi, who led the pre-World War II government, faced harsh criticism from the new leadership. In general, for China, the 20th century was fraught with crises. Initially, they were attacked one after another by European countries with large industries, and on the eve of World War II, close neighbors Russia and Japan attempted to colonize China. On October 1, 1949, the Communist Party of China established full control in the country, and Mao Zedong became the Chairman of the People's Republic of China. The reforms carried out by Mao Zedong in 1950 also paved the way for the Cultural Revolution. During this revolution, between 20 and 100 million people perished. This caused public discontent and led to the flight of Chinese investors abroad. The departure of investors from the country temporarily hindered development. Supporters of Chiang Kai-shek, who fled to Taiwan, proved with the help of the USA that the Asian continent could also become a region with developed industry. However, this did not have the slightest impact on the socio-economic and cultural situation of the Chinese population as a whole. As a result of the concentration of power in the hands of the dictator, economic, socio-cultural, and religious crises periodically occur in this country. In some cases, instances of ethnic discrimination are also observed in autonomous regions (Hong Kong, Macau, Inner Mongolia,

Xinjiang). At the same time, due to the availability of cheap labor, it became possible to produce modern technologies on a large scale within the country, which increased the interest of foreign investors in China. This factor has paved the way for China to become equal to the US over the past 40 years. The Chinese government skillfully took advantage of the 2019 pandemic (which is also a crisis situation in some areas). Internet pages such as "Kun.uz" and "Qalampir.uz" have repeatedly reported that the state, which once suffered as a result of colonialism, is now establishing economic control over the African continent and Central Asian countries through lending. China's attempts to establish control over other countries before fully recovering from its economic crises resemble the USSR's policy of the 1960s-1980s. Speaking of the USSR, it was the system created by the Bolsheviks, who overthrew the tsarist government in 1917 and came to power. It was the largest country of its time with a vast territory and huge economy. However, when it entered into competition with Europe and the USA, it made large investments in foreign countries, causing it to lose control of its internal situation. This led first to an economic crisis, then to a political one. In addition to these issues, ethnic, religious, and cultural crises periodically occurred within the country. The collapse of the USSR led to the formation of 15 independent states, excluding Russia.

Today, even in the example of the USA, which has the largest economy, we can observe that it has left many crises in its past. The recent fires in California have caused enormous damage to the US economy. We can see that this country's position on the world stage is gradually approaching a crisis, as evidenced in countries such as Lake Choson, the guerrilla wars in Vietnam, Afghanistan, and now Ukraine and Palestine. Internal discontent with the administration of Donald Trump, who won the last election, is currently growing. Moreover, China and its partner Russia have begun joint efforts to control the world stage against the US. An example of this is the recent creation of the international organization BRICS[4], a competitor to the NATO alliance. The fact that the newly elected US President, in his speeches, is claiming Canada and Greenland, which are alternative water reserves to Russia[5], indicates that the NATO organization is also undergoing an internal crisis. That is, the new US leader has shown that he could act against the interests of Canada and European countries. Of course, Otto von Bismarck, who united Germany as the 2nd Reich, said, "No country has friends"[6]. At the same time, we observe many developments and crises in German statehood. This state has repeatedly become the most powerful country in the world throughout its history. Examples include the era of Otto I of the Holy Roman Empire[7] and the period when Adolf Hitler seized power in recent history. In both periods, Germany became an unparalleled industrial-production and military power. After the reign of Otto I, the country began to weaken. Nine centuries later, Hitler came to the world stage, and a huge crisis occurred as a result of a multi-frontal war, following the agreement of the parties regarding his rule at the Tehran Conference[8].

When we think about countries that have fallen into crisis as a result of external intervention, Libya, Iraq, and Palestine come to mind first. Because their shared identity threatened the existence of a single Israel, the intervention of US forces led to the overthrow of the government and the unjust torture of its people. During the reign of Muammar Gaddafi[9], Libya was able to provide economic assistance to Islamic countries located in Africa and other parts of the world. Iraq, being very close to Israel, was considered a major threat to Israel. Saddam Hussein [10] left his mark on the country's economic development as a figure who came with enormous reforms. Unfortunately, US forces destroyed this country

under the UN flag. Modern societies have fully realized that the Israeli invasion, which reached its peak after 2023, was aimed at eliminating the country called Palestine from the world map. It is necessary to dwell on the above-mentioned USA once again. Deputies appointed by the US Parliament (Senators) and people's representatives play a major role in the election of the President to the government. We can witness that the effects of corruption in this country are benefiting Israel's interests.

In conclusion, countries with huge economies have also experienced many periods of crisis. However, there are cases of restraining newly emerging powers. In some cases, seemingly insignificant mistakes by the leadership of powerful countries can even lead to the crisis of that state. On the other hand, a state that today appears as a weak force can achieve enormous results. Examples include Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia, and South Korea. On the world stage, countries neighboring countries with huge economies and powerful armies may either develop or become doomed to backwardness and disappear from the world map. For example, we can observe that Mexico has become smaller than it was when it was first established, or we can observe Ukraine's current state. We are witnessing how most of the biased governments on the world stage lost their positions when they were left without the support of the power they relied on. Examples of this are the previous administrations of Syria and Afghanistan. For our country, we must correctly organize actions in the political arena and pursue a far-sighted policy.

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